

METHODS FOR EVALUATING THE STRATEGIES OF STATE-OWNED ENTERPRISES

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Abstract. *This article is aimed at identifying and developing tools for comprehensive diagnosis of strategy effectiveness, taking into account the interdependence of parameters describing various areas of enterprise activity, and forming an integrated indicator of strategic effectiveness.*

Keywords: *strategy development effectiveness, value approach, strategic planning.*

The general rules and criteria detailed in the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 14, 2022 PD-154 "On monitoring and assessing the openness of the activities of government agencies and organizations" fully reflect the essence of the strategy assessment. Based on an in-depth analysis of the situation, measures have been developed to further improve efficiency and effectiveness by eliminating the systemic causes and conditions of violations committed by government agencies and organizations in their activities to ensure transparency, as well as the widespread introduction of advanced international standards in this area.

It is known that particularly important factor is the solution to the problem of developing strategic planning tools. In such a situation, the decisions often made by managers are limited in improving the efficiency of financial activities and have a short-term effect. Long-term planning forces managers to develop more adaptive goals and solve problems taking into account changing internal and external business conditions. At the same time, enterprises facing fierce market competition need to optimize strategic work by enhancing the synergistic effect in all areas of their activities. In such conditions, the management of industrial enterprises needs to develop a set of development goals aimed at achieving overall strategic efficiency for each type of activity, as well as identify and develop synergistic links between departments. The solution to the problem requires the creation of a system to support independent decision-making, allowing for the coordination and control of the activities of all structural units.

Creating and maintaining such a match between the strategic resources of the organization and the constantly changing external environment require understanding and taking into account the key factors that determine the success of the organization. Having identified the most important competencies, you should focus on them in order to constantly improve the organization's efficiency in this area. Efficiency requires systems for analyzing and calculating these indicators, which should be as accurate and objective as possible. The essence of the concept of value-oriented management is that the company should be focused on ensuring the growth of the organization's market value and expected profit. All aspirations of organizations, analytical methods and management methods should be directed toward one common goal. This should help organizations maximize their value by building the management decision-making process around key value factors.

For this reason, the efficiency determines the degree of achievement of goals and planned results of development and implementation of economic, marketing, financial, social, innovative and other types of enterprise activities. In business, process efficiency characterizes its ability to respond to internal needs and is manifested as a result of interaction with external consumers and their interaction with each other, as well as interaction with the external environment of the enterprise. The influence of efficiency as a quality parameter is that the assessment of business processes reflects the degree of their implementation, describing how the process meets the goals, needs and expectations of the consumer or customer. Efficiency can be increased by improving or refining products. Depending on the services (products) that the company offers to the market, efficiency can be increased by redesigning or reengineering processes.

The efficiency of the system depends on how effectively the management is organized at the enterprise, that is, on the composition and number of departments, their subordination, distribution of functions. Thus, the efficiency of the management system determines not only the quality of managers, but also the quality of the organizational structure and management processes.

Performance efficiency is the ratio of management indicators and expended efforts, determined primarily by the managerial abilities of the manager and the degree of rational use of his powers in the organization.

For the purposes of this study, it is necessary to distinguish between the concepts of the strategic development efficiency assessment system and the organizational efficiency assessment system. Research analysis shows that the main differences lie in the approach to defining the subject of assessment and management levels. Traditional models of organizational efficiency assessment suggest measuring it by analyzing the processes of resource distribution and use. Here are the main indicators of labor productivity, return on assets, return on capital and equipment use. Common indicators in these models are indicators characterizing the efficiency of the financial and economic activities of the enterprise: profitability, turnover, sales growth.

The existing compromise between efficiency and effectiveness, determining the efficiency of choosing and implementing a strategy, can be assessed using special tools based on the principles of matrix analysis. Visualization of the dynamics and balance of the components of strategic efficiency is carried out using a polar coordinate system.

Companies in various industries operate in an extremely complex, uncertain and dynamic modern social and economic environment. The emergence of a global information market, where information about any product from any seller in any region of the world becomes available almost instantly, has led to a sharp increase in competition among business entities.

An inertial business management organization with a rigid structure does not allow for a quick response to constantly changing market demands. The main condition for sustainability and development in the competitive struggle is the ability of a business entity in the long term to consider and consistently implement various innovations in products and services, management, technology, etc.

To achieve a competitive advantage, a company must surpass competitors not only in all business processes, but also in overall efficiency. A clear strategy, expressed in terms of goals and indicators of business processes, should be aimed at meeting the expectations of customers and shareholders (investors). The top-down approach opens up completely new business processes that can help a company achieve excellence.

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